

Academic Hackathon and PBL as an Awakening of Competencies for Social Entrepreneurship in Engineering Students

Afsaneh Hamedí d'Escoffier¹, Frederico Pifano de Rezende^{2,3}

¹ Lab. Protozoologia, Instituto Oswaldo Cruz, Fundação Oswaldo Cruz, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil

² Texas A&M University

³ Instituto Federal do Espírito Santo, Espírito Santo, Brazil

Email: afsanehamedí@gmail.com, fredpifano@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060742>

Abstract

All over the world, there are social problems and needs that governmental, non-governmental, and market structures cannot recognize or respond to efficiently. In this context, social entrepreneurs fill this gap by finding innovative solutions and applying them with viable business models, considering social value and economic growth, and taking an above-average risk in creating and disseminating social value. Social entrepreneurship is a type of entrepreneurship, that shares similar sub-competencies such as discipline, innovation, risk-taking ability, etc. However, social entrepreneurship requires others, such as virtuosity, collaborative capacity, empathy, compassion, creative use of minimal resources, etc. Engineering professionals need to be aligned with these competencies, as they are involved with innovations, building infrastructure, and solving complex problems with a direct impact on communities. Texas A&M University annually promotes an academic hackathon called "Invent for the Planet" (IFTP), which brings together engineering students to seek solutions to proposed problems in 48 hours. During this period, students develop their projects according to the PBL methodology, actively seeking the necessary knowledge to present a prototype of the solution at the end of the process. Although the themes presented are varied, we observed a tendency for students to present solutions with a social bias, with, in some cases, the subsequent creation of startups to produce the developed artifacts. In this article, we present a success story, from a group from Brazilian universities that, during the IFTP, developed an electronic cane for the blind, which gave rise to a startup of products focused on accessibility. Through semi-structured interviews and focus groups with the participating students, we concluded that PBL was decisive in awakening specific sub-competencies for social entrepreneurship. Therefore, we propose the use of academic hackathons in engineering education as provocative tools for the development of competencies for social entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Social Entrepreneurship, Project-Based Learning; Academic Hackathon; Engineering Education.

1 Introduction

Since Schumpeter's seminal work was published in 1911, entrepreneurship has been a well-defined area within economic theory (Swedberg, 2000). However, social entrepreneurship was not initially central to this theory and was rarely covered in textbooks, magazines, and articles on entrepreneurship. Certo and Miller (2008) define social entrepreneurship as a process that recognizes, evaluates, and explores opportunities to generate social value, including the provision of basic needs such as food, health, and education. Social entrepreneurship has community goals and seeks profitability to reinvest in the organization (Steinerowski, Jack, & Farmer, 2008). It is most common in contexts with socioeconomic, environmental, and cultural challenges, offering sustainable solutions to social problems (Dacin et al., 2010; Nga & Shamuganathan, 2010).

Globally, social challenges often do not receive an effective response from governmental, non-governmental, and market institutions due to budget constraints, bureaucracy, and lack of capacity to innovate and adapt to the specific needs of communities. In this context, social entrepreneurs emerge to fill this gap, offering innovative solutions to problems such as poverty, inequality, lack of education, social exclusion, and environmental impacts. They apply viable business models, considering both social value and economic

growth, taking an above-average risk in the conception and dissemination of social value, something that governments often avoid due to the pressure for immediate results. Furthermore, they can personalize their approaches, adapting them to the cultural, linguistic, and social particularities of each context. They identify flaws in society and turn them into business opportunities, recruiting and motivating others to their cause and building networks with essential people. They face obstacles and introduce their systems to manage their social businesses.

Social entrepreneurship shares some competencies common to entrepreneurship, such as discipline, innovation, and willingness to take risks. However, it requires additional skills, such as virtuosity, collaborative ability, empathy, compassion, and creative use of minimal resources, making a multidimensional analysis necessary in its study. Generally, social entrepreneurship competence is made up of five measurable dimensions or sub-competences: personal characteristics, leadership, social innovation, social value, and entrepreneurial management (Vázquez-Parra et al., 2021). Engineering professionals need to develop these competencies as they are involved in innovations, building infrastructure, and solving complex problems that directly impact communities.

There is a consensus that entrepreneurship is a skill that can be acquired, as it is possible to develop programs and courses that lead students to understand and structure contexts, as well as understand the stages in the evolution of entrepreneurship (Filion, 1999). Likewise, according to Freire (2001), through educational practice, students can perceive the social, political, and technological context of the reality of socially excluded people and understand the possibility of changing this situation through collective actions. As a teaching methodology, Freire proposes to address the problems faced by organizations and communities in which they operate, so that they can understand reality and, based on this, jointly propose conditions for social change.

In this context, universities are called upon to play a crucial role in promoting entrepreneurial behavior (Liguori and Winkler, 2020; Ndou et al., 2018; Secundo et al., 2021) through personalized education and incubator management to individuals who develop and share innovative ideas for social entrepreneurship (Solomon et al., 2019; Ratten and Jones, 2021; Secundo et al., 2021). However, several factors and challenges affect the effective development of competencies, knowledge, and entrepreneurial skills relevant to the creation of innovative ventures with social impact (Ndou et al., 2018; Lawrence et al., 2012; Vázquez-Parra et al., 2021).

In non-formal education, learning occurs interactively and intentionally, with objectives that are not previously established, but rather constructed through collective processes that generate social capital (Gohn, 2013; Willems, 2015). Social entrepreneurship exemplifies non-formal education, as it promotes the creation of a collective identity within a specific community; reconfigures the understanding of the world; prepares individuals to face life's challenges; helps to reinforce self-valuation and acquire practical knowledge, thus contributing to the development of social capital (Gohn, 2013; Iturrioz; Aragón; Narvaiza, 2015).

Training through project development is an effective strategy for developing these competencies. A widely used methodology is Problem/Project Based Learning (PBL), which is based on working on projects based on authentic problems. Students apply theory and knowledge acquired through research to projects, being responsible for their learning. Initially, they are presented with broad themes related to real-life issues and then they organize themselves into small groups to identify problems related to the proposed themes. Students search for solutions autonomously, prototype, test, and present their solutions to classmates and teachers. Mentor teachers continuously supervise these learning cycles, guiding and correcting routes, without offering ready-made solutions (GRAAF & KOLMOS, 2007; BENDER, 2012; KOKOTSAKY, MENZIES, & WIGGINS, 2016).

In the same line of thought, hackathons or bootcamps emerge as strategies for generating new ideas, products, or processes. These events begin with a challenge that requires the development of projects in a short period,

often less than 48 hours. Despite its brevity, during the experience, all the fundamental steps for developing a PBL project are covered. Furthermore, hackathons are characterized by an emphasis on innovation, necessary due to competition and the rapid obsolescence of products.

Academic hackathons can be considered a subgroup of PBL activities, being called short-term PBL (d'Escoffier, d'Escoffier & Braga, 2022). The College of Engineering at Texas A&M University (TAMU) has been promoting short-term events focused on training in innovation and entrepreneurship for some time (Boehm, 2020). These events, known as "Aggies", aim to immerse students in a structured, intensive, and innovative design experience. In 2018, TAMU expanded this event model, which was already successful with its students, to a global scale, resulting in "Invent for the Planet" (IFTP), based on the "Aggies" model. IFTP challenges students from around the world to find solutions to problems provided by international institutions.

In this study, we investigated a group of students from Brazilian universities who, after winning an IFTP by proposing mobility devices for blind people, founded a startup focused on producing low-cost accessibility products. Through semi-structured interviews and focus groups, we sought to understand whether academic hackathons and PBL were decisive in awakening in students the demand for the development of sub-skills for social entrepreneurship. This data will be used to create educational strategies and initiatives designed to develop these skills and values among students.

2 Methodology

2.1 The case

A team made up of 6 students from the electrical and mechanical engineering course at the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro and CEFET/RJ won the 2019 IFTP with an accessibility project, made up of 2 artifacts that guide blind people on their daily commute. The first was a cap with sensors that allowed it to identify obstacles ahead. The other was a sensor that, when pointed in certain directions, allowed the detection of holes (electronic cane), both low-cost artifacts. After the event, the team decided to create a startup to commercialize that product. They later expanded their concept into an accessibility solutions company.

2.2 Data collection and analysis

The first stage of data collection was a virtual interview with one of the team members who played a leadership role in the process. During the interview, we seek to learn about the experience from this student's point of view. Based on the information provided to him, a second stage was scheduled, which consisted of a virtual focus group with all startup participants. To resolve some issues, individual virtual interviews were carried out with three members of the group.

The questions raised in the focus group were organized based on the information given in the interview using a semi-structured question model. The use of this methodology aimed to obtain a collective mental reconstruction of the process the students went through. During this process, each student could talk about their experience in the process and compare it with that of their peers. This information collection technique allows for a more reliable reconstruction of the facts, as it is shared by everyone who lived the experience. Individual meetings were conducted with specific questions to the members to clarify details that were not clear in the focus group.

The reports were analyzed qualitatively (Morgan, 1997), using a methodological approach inspired by content analysis, to identify indicators (quantitative or not) that would allow inferences about the conditions of production and reception of these messages (inferred variables) (Bardin, 1977). Based on this analysis, the information was organized into analysis categories.

At all stages, the students participated voluntarily.

3 Results

Participation in IFTP was encouraged by its teachers, with no immediate interest. At first, they believed that they would participate in some type of training activity in which their technical skills would be required. The entrepreneurial perspective or the creation of a startup never crossed their minds, although the topic of entrepreneurship arouses some curiosity. In essence, they attended the event out of respect for the teachers. Therefore, there was no contact with entrepreneurial or innovation training during the course.

The group's choice of the theme "Increased quality of life" was random, as the mother of one of the members worked with children with special needs. During the interview, we realized that there was a desire to produce something that would reach the target audience, without any idea of the role of entrepreneurship in the process. They developed two interdependent accessories that guide blind people on their daily journey. The first was a cap with sensors that allowed it to identify obstacles ahead. The other was a sensor that, when pointed in certain directions, allowed the detection of holes (electronic cane). The idea for creating the product arose from the team members' ability to use sensors.

"...our prototype was not to cure blindness, but to improve the quality of life of these people." (Student 1, mechanical engineering).

The victory in the regional section signaled the product's usefulness and practicality. Confident in the quality of the project, the group took advantage of the one month until the trip to TAMU to participate in the final, to improve the prototype, making it more efficient and visually more attractive. They also tested the prototype with a blind person. At this point, they had time to delve deeper into the topic and, as a consequence, they began to realize the social importance of the product, as we can see in the statement below:

"When we saw people with disabilities using our equipment, which we had produced quickly, we were very happy and saw that the product worked. We had managed to improve the life of that disabled person..." (Student 4, mechanical engineering).

By becoming IFTP champions, they felt confident in the quality of the product and recognized the possibility of its commercialization. Thus, the group decided that they wanted to set up their own company, despite their insecurity about the venture:

"Until now we didn't have any ideas and, can we do something beyond that?..." (Student 3, mechanical engineering).

However, despite all the difficulties encountered, including having to initially maintain and manage the business with its resources, the group did not give up and, with the proceeds from the sale of the first units that were being sold, they created other low-cost products aimed at accessibility, such as a card with data about the person with a disability that can be accessed by anyone who wants to obtain information about the person, without the need to fill out forms or speak orally, and a Tag with the same functions as the card.

According to the students' speech, it is clear that the experience at the event stimulated thinking about social entrepreneurship, making them look beyond what traditional training can offer:

"It's not worth going to college just to get a good grade, close the academy, and get a diploma at the end. If you do that, you won't add anything... I don't think it adds much to what you can build." (Student 2, electrical engineering).

"We only managed to do it because there was all the organization of the event..." (Student 4, mechanical engineering).

4 Discussion

Entrepreneurial education is a crucial component for new markets. Encouraging young people to start their businesses is essential for the economic growth of the country and institutions. Students who participate in courses focused on entrepreneurship are more likely to engage in activities and ideas for new ventures (Bergmann, 2018). Furthermore, entrepreneurial education is one of the missions of education, alongside teaching, research, and economic development through business technology or the creation of companies by students and teachers (García et al., 2017).

We currently recognize that education plays a central and catalytic role in social change, especially in areas where social problems such as poverty or social exclusion are evident. This understanding has led to the emergence of educational initiatives aimed at addressing the causes of these problems, making both formal and non-formal education fertile ground for the creation and dissemination of innovative social initiatives. Meaningful learning is fundamental, as it is through it that individuals develop and mobilize new attitudes (Parente, 2014).

According to García-Gonzales & Ramírez-Montoya (2020), social entrepreneurship education focuses on personal development, identifying opportunities, and searching for solutions to social or environmental problems. Engineers, as producers of innovation, are fundamental players in contributing to social entrepreneurship, hence the importance of developing this sub-competence in engineering courses.

Given this, the creation of academic hackathons is a good idea for using non-formal education to encourage innovation and entrepreneurship. However, although there are hundreds of this hackathon model taking place every year in several universities around the world (DEVPOST, 2023), few works arising from these events become startups. Hence the importance of studying the case presented here.

The IFTP winning team had the opportunity to develop a low-cost product aimed at people with special needs. During the event, there was a need for theoretical deepening not only for the development of the artifact, with the consequent development of technical skills (hard skills) but also for the search for knowledge that justified the creation of the product. At this point, skills at a behavioral level (soft skills) could be developed, including the sub-competence of social entrepreneurship. This can be confirmed by the fact that, in the beginning, although they had casually had the idea of producing a device for social purposes, the idea of starting a business with this product never crossed the students' minds.

How the IFTP event is conducted can be considered as a short-term PBL, by aligning with its phases. It is well-studied that PBL is capable of developing specific competencies in students (Kolmos & Fink, 2004). In our study, this became clear when the students stated that they started at the event with no prospects and, when they left, they opened a startup focused on accessibility.

Therefore, the PBL methodology associated with the dynamics of an academic hackathon is capable of awakening in students not only awareness of the importance of developing certain skills but also the desire to become entrepreneurs.

Therefore, if we implement hackathons organized in PBL format in educational environments, with themes that seek innovative solutions to social, environmental, and cultural problems, we can have a generation prone to social entrepreneurship, contributing to the creation of a fairer, more inclusive, and sustainable world.

We are aware that the period of a hackathon, in our case 48 hours, is limited for the complete development of skills. However, it is capable of stimulating students in their progress, as evidenced by students' comments, when they realize the effectiveness of the prototype in improving the quality of life of a blind person, or when they recognize the role of the engineer in contributing to the construction of something meaningful to society.

5 Conclusion

The case presented demonstrates that skills for social entrepreneurship can be developed through non-formal educational initiatives in the training of engineers. IFTP is an international event led by Texas A&M that brings together several institutions, whose main role is to train students in innovation and entrepreneurship. This event was able to awaken a vision of social entrepreneurship in a group of students so this group opened a startup focused on low-cost products for accessibility.

We also concluded that the PBL methodology was fundamental to success, given that students when guided through the PBL phases, were able to identify problems within the reality around them, seek solutions for them, and produce a functional prototype. Also, when they felt the need to look for indications that justified their product, they had access to information related to previously unnoticed scenarios, expanding their vision of society's problems.

Therefore, we propose the use of academic hackathons in PBL format in engineering education as provocative tools for the development of competencies for social entrepreneurship.

6 References

- Bardin, L. (1977). *Análise de conteúdo*. Lisboa: Edições 70.
- Bender, W. N. (2012). *Project-Based Learning: Differentiating Instruction for the 21st Century*. Corwin.
- Bergmann, H., Geissler, M., Hundt, C., & Grave, B. (2018). The climate for entrepreneurship at higher education institutions. *Research Policy*, 47(4), 700-716.
- Certo, S., & Miller, T. (2008). Social entrepreneurship: Key issues and concepts. *Business Horizons*, 51, 267-271.
- Dacin, P., Dacin, M., & Matear, M. (2010). Social entrepreneurship: Why we don't need a new theory and how we move forward from here. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 38-57.
- d'Escoffier, A. H., d'Escoffier, L. N., & Braga, M. (2022). Intensive innovation experience: which skills can be activated using a short-term PBL project? *Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 9(1), 26-36.
- Devpost. (n.d.). The home for hackathons. Retrieved from <https://devpost.com>
- Filion, L. J. (1999). Empreendedorismo: empreendedores e proprietários-gerentes de pequenos negócios. *Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 34(2), 5-28.
- Freire, P. (2001). *Pedagogia dos sonhos possíveis*. São Paulo: UNESP.
- García, J. C. S., Ward, A., Hernández, B., & Florez, J. L. (2017). Entrepreneurship Education: State of the Art. *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 5(2), 401-473.
- García-González, A., & Ramírez-Montoya, M. S. (2023). Social Entrepreneurship Competency in Higher Education: An Analysis Using Mixed Methods. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, 14(1), 91-109.
- Gohn, M. G. (2013). *Educação não formal e o educador social: atuação no desenvolvimento de projetos sociais*. São Paulo: Cortez.
- Graaf, E., & Kolmos, A. (2007). History of problem-based and project-based learning. In E. Graaf & A. Kolmos (Eds.), *Management of Change* (pp. 1-8). Rotterdam: Sense Publ.
- Iturrioz, C., Aragón, C., & Narvaiza, L. (2015). How to foster shared innovation within SMEs' networks: Social capital and the role of intermediaries. *European Management Journal*, 33(2), 104-115.
- Kokotsaky, D., Menzies, V., & Wiggins, A. (2016). Project-based learning: a review of the literature. *Improving Schools*, 19(3), 267-277.
- Kolmos, A., & Fink, F. K. (2004). *The Aalborg PBL Model: Progress, Diversity, and Challenges*. Edited by L. Krogh. Aalborg: Aalborg University Press.
- Lawrence, T., Phillips, N., & Tracey, P. (2012). From the guest editors: Educating social entrepreneurs and social innovators. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 11, 319-323.
- Liguori, E., & Winkler, C. (2020). From offline to online: Challenges and opportunities for entrepreneurship education following the COVID-19 pandemic. *Entrepreneurship Education and Pedagogy*, 3, 346-351.
- Morgan, D. L. (1997). *Focus groups as qualitative research*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications.

- Ndou, V., Secundo, G., Schiuma, G., & Passiante, G. (2018). Insights for shaping entrepreneurship education: Evidence from the European entrepreneurship centers. *Sustainability*, 10, 4323.
- Nga, J., & Shamuganathan, G. (2010). The influence of personality traits and demographic factors on social entrepreneurship startup intentions. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 95, 259-282.
- Parente, C. (2014). Empreendedorismo social em Portugal. Ed. Universidade do Porto – Faculdade de Letras.
- Ratten, V., & Jones, P. (2021). Covid-19 and entrepreneurship education: Implications for advancing research and practice. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 19, 100432.
- Secundo, G., Gioconda, M., Del Vecchio, P., Gianluca, E., Margherita, A., & Ndou, V. (2021). Threat or opportunity? A case study of digital-enabled redesign of entrepreneurship education in the COVID-19 emergency. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 166, 120565.
- Solomon, G. T., Alabduljader, N., & Ramani, R. S. (2019). Knowledge management and social entrepreneurship education: Lessons learned from an exploratory two-country study. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23, 10.
- Steinerowski, A., Jack, S., & Farmer, J. (2008). Who are the social entrepreneurs and what do they actually do? Babson College Entrepreneurship Research Conference (BCERC). *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, 28(21), Article 2.
- Swedberg, R. (2000). The social science view of entrepreneurship: introduction and practical applications. In R. Swedberg (Ed.), *Entrepreneurship: The social science view*. New York: The Oxford University Press.
- Vázquez-Parra, J. C., García-González, A., & Ramírez-Montoya, M. S. (2021). Social entrepreneurship competency: An approach by discipline and gender. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 13(5), 1357-1373.
- Willems, J. (2015). Individual perceptions on the participant and societal functionality of non-formal education for youth: explaining differences across countries based on the human development index. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 44(C), 11-20.